

Assessment of carbon stocks and CO₂ sequestration rate through urban trees in city Faisalabad, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Urban trees serve as CO₂ emissions absorbers resulting from activities of human in the city, as well as an indicator of atmospheric quality and a pollution scouting device. The importance of trees in the planning process for the sustainable development of cities cannot be overstated. The purpose of this study was to assess the potential of “carbon stocks” and tree stands in Faisalabad that had the highest carbon stock and CO₂ sequestration rates. The study was carried out in September-November 2019 in the Faisalabad city area covering 20 locations. The biomass calculation and carbon stock estimation is based on Diameter at Breast Height (DBH) is measuring by utilizing an “allometric equation $B = 0.11 \rho D^{(2+0.62)}$ ”. Allometric equations containing the definite wood density of each tree species are used in data processing. The findings depicted, potential of “carbon stocks” in Faisalabad trees is 34.782 ± 41.84 kg/ha with Jinnah Park, and Razabad is 5.033 ± 2.70 kg/ha. Overall, the maximum CO₂ sequestration rate is 16.096 ± 16.37 kg/ha/year and the minimum in Razabad with 1.893 ± 1.13 kg/ha/year. However, the total “carbon stock” and CO₂ sequestration rate were more in densely vegetated areas than the poorly vegetated area. Atmospheric quality in high vegetation areas was much improved as compared to that in less vegetated areas.

Keywords: Urban Trees, DBH, Estimation, Allometric Equations, Wood Density

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INTRODUCTION

The last century has been characterized by urbanization, with the towns and metropolitan cities expanding worldwide both in size and number (Ritchie, 2018). More than 50% of the world population is presently dwelling in cities and these numbers are rapidly growing at a rate of 4% per decade till 2050 (Tang *et al.*, 2016; UN, 2016). Among different regions of the world, countries from Asia and Africa are being urbanized much faster than European countries. However, Asia has the most

significant number of people residing in (cities and towns) and contains 53 percent of the world's urban population (UN, 2014).

Urban areas are frequently exposed to anthropogenic disturbances and subsequently characterized by dynamic habitats. This human-made degradation of the ecosystem varies along with urbanization gradients (Feng *et al.*, 2018). Growing urban sprawls are presently contributing approximately 80% of the total global economy by exhausting 70% of energy and releasing a significant amount of global energy emissions (Seto *et al.*, 2017). So, temperature, air, and soil pollution, soil sealing, soil alkalinity, compaction, noise pollution, CO₂ concentration increased with population density, however water quality and availability decline with urbanization intensity (McKinney, 2002; George *et al.*, 2007; Pataki *et al.*, 2007). Consequently, the ratio of natural and semi-natural habitats decreases over time. Urban sustainable development has been at the core of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDG, 2015) and the Paris Agreement, 2015 on climate change (Kawakubo *et al.*, 2018).

Cities are an important source of “C” emissions with a dense human population (UN Habitat, 2011). Managing and developing cities pose an immense challenge for human welfare. Significant climate change adaptation and mitigation are urgently required to be included and applied in these growing sprawls. Trees are among the plant species that can help to enhance urban air value by absorbing pollutants such as “carbon dioxide”. This compound is absorbed and transformed into “biomass” (Salsabillah *et al.*, 2021). The amount of “carbon sequestration” is described by a number of factors, including the number of people present, “carbon” pollution levels, the length of the in-leaf season, and rainfall (Dahlan, 1992).

The creation of urban forests is one of the efforts to absorb “carbon” in urban settings. Urban woods provide a variety of purposes, including preserving flora and fauna, reducing pollution, and storing “carbon” (Sedjarawan, 2014). In greater detail, the urban forest contributes to “carbon sequestration” in two ways: as “carbon” and heat absorbent agents, and as “carbon” and heat absorbent agents. As a result of the heat absorption, the air temperature will be lowered, resulting in an increase in the efficiency of electricity usage for air conditioners, lowering “carbon emissions” (Lubis *et al.*, 2013).

Forests can store “carbon” in five different carbon pools: the lithosphere, seas, soil organic matter, atmosphere, and biosphere (Aisyah, 2013; Gülçin *et al.*, 2021). The tree stand is an example of aboveground biomass. Trees in the forest can absorb “carbon” in the form of “carbon dioxide” and store it as biomass through photosynthesis. As a result, the link between forest biomass and “carbon” content becomes more complicated (Febiriyanti *et al.*, 2021). Because of its critical role in the “carbon biogeochemical cycle”, forest biomass has also been linked to climate change (BSN, 2011).

However, no knowledge on updated “carbon stocks” or that tree species give the highest carbon stock is available. The study was meant to investigate the role of urban trees in “carbon” capture and “CO₂ reduction”, keeping the importance of the issue in mind. The current investigation was conducted in Faisalabad, with the primary goal of determining the precise distribution of “carbon” above and below ground. The “carbon stocks” amount and the tree species with the highest “carbon

stocks” in the city area are vital to determine (Babbar *et al.*, 2021). A study like this is necessary to determine the quantity of potential “carbon stock/year”.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The study was conducted on September-November 2019 in Faisalabad city. The city area was divided into 20 location sites, which cover the residential area, educational institutions, parks, hospitals, and commercial area. There were twenty all sample sites, urban trees were divided into “200 sample sites” with a “100 m x 100 m² plot” for each sample (BSN, 2011).

DETERMINATION OF VEGETATION AREA

The city area was calculated using the programme “ArcGIS 10.5 version” based on “GPS coordinate data”, then inserted in a “Google Earth map”, converted to a shape-file format, then opened in “ArcGIS software”. The area of Faisalabad is calculated using ArcGIS software (figure 1).

URBAN TREES DATA COLLECTION

In the realm of non-destructive sampling, data on urban trees was collected using the direct measuring method. By using a normal measuring tape, the diameter breast height (DBH) of all stands that goes into the “plot” was measured at “1.3 m” from the soil's surface and then converted to a “diameter”.

CLIMATIC PARAMETER DATA RETRIEVAL

Climate statistics gathered is supplementary material for determining climatic elements and as a reason in calculating the number of “carbon reserves”. The percentage of “relative humidity” and “air temperature” were measured using a Small Weather Station and an Air Quality Monitor at each sample site, which is located in the middle of the sampling locations.

PROCESSING AND DATA ANALYSIS

The first step in data processing is to convert tree circumference into diameters (DBH), which is then divided by 3.14. The diameter obtained was used to compute the “biomass” of all tree stand using the “allometric equation $B = 0.11 D (2 + 0.62)$ ” (Ketterings *et al.*, 2011) with “ $W =$ tree biomass (kg); $=$ wood density (g/cm³) (ICRAF, 2017); $D =$ tree diameter (cm)”. After obtaining the biomass, the carbon stock is computed using the equation by multiplying the biomass by the 0.5 coefficient: “ $C = W * 0.5$ with $C =$ carbon stock (ton); $W =$ tree biomass (kg)” (Brown, 1997).

The data was processed using the Microsoft Excel application, which included entering the biomass and carbon stock values. The data was then examined by comparing carbon stores in sample sites and comparing “carbon stocks” in each tree species to determine which tree species had the maximum “carbon stock”.

Figure 1: Map of Pakistan with administrative boundaries and Faisalabad city map.

Figure 2: Faisalabad city map with their twenty working sites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results regarding urban tree density, species richness, total carbon stock, total CO₂, CO₂ sequestration rate per hectare per year, and soil compaction have been presented in Table 1. The maximum urban tree density (24.1) and species richness (8.2) per hectare on average were found in Jinnah Park. This was followed by (18.5) and (8.1) in Kaleem Shaheed Park (KSP) and (14.6) and (5.6) trees per hectare and species richness respectively in the University of Agriculture Faisalabad (UAF).

However, the minimum urban tree density and species richness were observed in the Razaabad location site with an average tree density of (4.1) and species richness of (2.2) per hectare on average. Results revealed that CO₂ sequestration ranged from 18.437 to 127.409 kg ha⁻¹, whereas total carbon stock at all sites varied from 5.839 to 34.782 kg ha⁻¹. All of these CO₂ parameters were higher in the Jinnah Park location site as compared with others. The mean maximum total carbon stock (34.782 kg ha⁻¹), total CO₂ sequestration (127.409 kg ha⁻¹) and total CO₂ sequestration rate (16.096 kg ha⁻¹ per year) were estimated in Jinnah Park followed by KSP and UAF. However, the least total carbon stock (5.033 kg ha⁻¹), total CO₂ sequestration (18.437 kg ha⁻¹), and total CO₂ sequestration rate (1.893 kg ha⁻¹ per year) were recorded in the location of Razaabad, Faisalabad.

In the case of soil compaction, the results depicted that the maximum soil compaction (0.590 kg/cm²) was estimated in Jinnah Park, followed by KSP and UAF with soil compaction of 0.487 and 0.432 kg/cm² respectively. However, the minimum soil compaction (0.210 kg/cm²) was estimated in Razabad and followed by Tariqabad 0.22 kg/cm².

CARBON STOCK, CARBON SEQUESTRATION RATE, AND SOIL COMPACTION IN FAISALABAD

Although all the selected sites of the study area had more or less similar environmental conditions the amount of carbon stock and CO₂ sequestered by urban trees was slightly different. This was due to the different number of tree species and the basal area across all the study sites. The site with a greater number of trees, greater DBH, and, height had the greater amount of total carbon. Our results are in agreement with previous studies (Boffa, 1999; Bayal *et al.*, 2011; Marone *et al.*, 2017). It was reported that as the trees increase in size, the accumulation in biomass and size also increased. This increase in biomass and size of tree species will ultimately result in higher “carbon stocks” (Stephenson *et al.*, 2014). As urban trees are mostly planted for recreation and for getting shade, so, trees are pruned on regular basis, once or twice a year which results in comparatively less carbon storage as compared to those planted for timber purposes. Takimoto (2008 a) examined different silviculture systems including home gardens in Mali and found that parklands have larger “carbon stocks” than live fences and fodder banks because parklands have older trees with larger DBH. While live fences and fodder banks despite having more trees ha⁻¹ have less storage of carbon in them because the branches were pruned to control the tree height i.e. (< 4 m). Moreover, the capacity of various tree species to store carbon depends on a number of components such as tree type, distribution, structure, growth pattern, and functions within the system (Schroeder, 1994; Albrecht and Kandji, 2003).

Tree density also plays an important role in determining the number of “carbon stocks” and carbon sequestration. For example, 5 years old poplar trees with 250 trees ha⁻¹ captured about 7.8 t C ha⁻¹ (Fang *et al.*, 2010). In the present study, the maximum tree density was observed in Jinnah Park (24.1 trees ha⁻¹) capturing an amount of 34.782 kg C ha⁻¹, much lesser than the amount reported by Fang *et al.* (2010). As tree density plays an important role in the exact estimation of tree biomass, so there has always been a linear relationship between the two (Ajit *et al.*, 2016). Murthy *et al.* (2013) estimated farm tree biomass and tree carbon stock in two states of India: Karnataka and Tamil Nadu. The findings of their study are in line with the above-reported results as the amount of carbon captured across all study sites ranged from 5.033 kg C ha⁻¹ (Razabad) to 34.782 kg C ha⁻¹ (Jinnah Park).

Urban trees are additionally pruned on regular basis, so their branch's structure and arrangement are different as compared to forest or timber trees. So far, no research work has explained the effect of pruning on biomass accumulation and carbon stock of urban trees. Tree pruning in urban residential colonies may result in less diameter and length of the upper crown of various tree species. Compared to semi-natural ecosystems, urban area vegetation is majorly generated by artificial plantations and subsequent alteration of different species. Certain different techniques also involve the removal of debris and old pruned shoots below the trees, extensive training and pruning, management of fertilization, and irrigation practices (Nowak and Crane, 2002).

However, it is not necessary that trees with greater carbon stock have greater carbon sequestration potential (Takimoto, 2007). The carbon sequestration potential of this study varied from 18.437 kg C ha⁻¹ (Razabad) to 127.09 kg C ha⁻¹ (Jinnah Park). This range was in accordance with the range reported by Ng (2012). Similarly, in three cities of Korea, the carbon storage ranged from 0.47 to 0.72 kg m⁻² in woody plants of urban areas (Jo, 2002). This measured amount of carbon in Korean cities is slightly higher as described in the current study. More or less similar results have been documented by Zhao *et al.* (2010) in urban tree cover of Hangzhou, China with an average amount of 4.28 kg C m⁻² and Raciti *et al.* (2012) in Boston urban area (10.6 kg C m⁻²) in trees with DBH >5 cm. However, the annual carbon sequestration rate in the above-mentioned areas was much higher as compared to our findings due to higher growth rates of various species as compared to the studied area. In Barcelona, Spain, the estimated average aboveground urban carbon stock was 4.45 kg C m⁻² but this amount varied from 1.53 kg C m⁻² of vegetation in industrial areas to 9.67 kg C m⁻² of vegetation in institutional areas. Though, in present study above ground carbon density rates varied from 3.994 kg C ha⁻¹ of vegetated areas to 27.605 kg C ha⁻¹ of vegetation in the park and educational institute, this amount is slightly lower than that described by Chapparro and Terradas (2009). Similar findings have also been reported in various parts of the world e.g. Strohbach and Hasse (2012) in Leipzig, Germany (0.68 kg C m⁻²), Nowak *et al.* (2008); Nowak *et al.* (2011), and Nowak *et al.* (2012b) in various cities of USA.

Carbon storage potential and sequestration potential from previous literature suggest that urban trees result in altering the carbon emission levels in urban areas. Planting trees at different energy emissions locations and around such buildings can help to overcome such pollution (Heisler, 1986). Transpirational cooling and changes

in albedo can vary the climate of the urban area which often also results in the reduction of carbon emissions from cities. In addition, when estimating the net impact of urban trees on atmospheric CO₂, urban tree management practices need to be considered because various maintenance activities emit carbon back into the atmosphere through the burning of fossil fuels (such as chain saws, trucks, and cutting machines) (Nowak *et al.*, 2002). As urban areas generate a large number of carbon emissions, it is necessary to combine the impact of trees on carbon emissions through changes in microclimate, albedo, energy use, and maintenance emissions with the estimation of tree storage and sequestration in order to assess the impact of urban forests on climate change.

Planting density has a major effect on soil properties particularly the topsoil layer is mainly eroded or affected. The results of the experiment concluded that increasing tree population in Faisalabad city will help to improve the soil physio-chemical properties of soil and also reduce the soil nutrients losses that in turn help to the sustainability of the long life of urban trees. Compaction increases soil bulk density and permeability resistance and reduces soil macroporosity, aeration, infiltration, and water storage (Silva, 2005). The decrease in soil infiltration due to the compaction of the surface layer will lead to an increase in surface runoff and erosion.

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Table 1: Urban forest inventory, species richness, total carbon stock, CO₂ sequestration, CO₂ sequestration rate and soil compaction

Sr. No	Location Site	Tree Density ha ⁻¹	Species Richness ha ⁻¹	Total Carbon (kg)ha ⁻¹	CO ₂ (kg) ha ⁻¹	CO ₂ Sequestration rate kg/ha/year	Soil Compaction (kg/cm ²)
1	Jinnah Park	24.1 ± 11.3	8.2 ± 3.15	34.782 ± 41.84	127.409 ± 153.2	16.096 ± 16.37	0.590 ± 0.22
2	D-Ground	9.3 ± 5.47	4 ± 1.88	7.009 ± 10.99	25.675 ± 40.27	3.192 ± 3.79	0.309 ± 0.10
3	Tariqabad	4.3 ± 1.49	2.8 ± 0.91	5.515 ± 3.50	20.201 ± 12.84	1.995 ± 1.22	0.229 ± 0.01
4	Millat Town	5.3 ± 2.75	3.5 ± 1.35	8.597 ± 5.95	31.494 ± 21.82	3.392 ± 2.24	0.239 ± 0.03
5	People colony	6.7 ± 3.30	3 ± 1.24	10.738 ± 9.61	39.336 ± 35.20	4.382 ± 3.77	0.252 ± 0.04
6	Samanabad	5.1 ± 1.66	2.9 ± 0.87	5.839 ± 5.50	21.391 ± 20.18	2.012 ± 1.96	0.237 ± 0.02

7	Machli Farm	6.3 ± 4.83	2.9 ± 1.28	8.342 ± 6.33	30.55 ± 23.20	3.098 ± 2.50	0.266 ± 0.08
8	Gulfishan colony	5.2 ± 3.55	2.4 ± 1.42	11.922 ± 15.96	43.67 ± 58.49	4.504 ± 6.66	0.256 ± 0.06
9	Chenab Chowk	5.4 ± 2.22	2.8 ± 0.78	8.665 ± 7.31	31.74 ± 26.80	3.302 ± 2.73	0.264 ± 0.03
10	KSP	18.5 ± 9.22	8.1 ± 2.90	29.475 ± 28.82	107.96 ± 105.57	11.859 ± 10.90	0.487 ± 0.15
11	Nazimabad	6.3 ± 3.09	2.7 ± 1.05	14.598 ± 10.48	53.476 ± 38.41	5.154 ± 4.23	0.281 ± 0.05
12	Gulberg	8.7 ± 4.27	4.1 ± 2.80	14.651 ± 7.23	53.669 ± 26.50	6.088 ± 3.21	0.322 ± 0.07
13	Allied Chowk	4.7 ± 1.94	2.5 ± 1.08	6.126 ± 2.80	22.441 ± 10.27	2.409 ± 1.02	0.253 ± 0.03
14	Wapda Town	5.3 ± 2.49	2.5 ± 0.84	8.028 ± 5.44	29.408 ± 19.94	2.967 ± 1.71	0.258 ± 0.04
15	GMA	7.5 ± 2.63	3.2 ± 1.13	11.739 ± 9.20	43.001 ± 33.71	4.500 ± 4.076	0.297 ± 0.04
16	Razabad	4.1 ± 1.59	2.2 ± 0.78	5.033 ± 2.70	18.437 ± 9.91	1.893 ± 1.13	0.210 ± 0.03
17	Muhammadpur	4.7 ± 2.26	2.7 ± 0.82	7.417 ± 6.91	27.170 ± 25.31	2.669 ± 2.30	0.245 ± 0.03
18	Nishatabad	5.8 ± 2.34	2.8 ± 0.78	9.911 ± 5.05	36.304 ± 18.50	3.587 ± 1.78	0.267 ± 0.03
19	Madina Town	7.4 ± 2.63	2.9 ± 0.73	9.169 ± 5.99	33.587 ± 21.97	3.472 ± 2.07	0.302 ± 0.04
20	UAF	14.6 ± 11.26	5.6 ± 3.74	17.260 ± 16.02	63.225 ± 58.70	6.646 ± 6.35	0.432 ± 0.21